

Bio-Waste-Derived Adsorbent Materials for Methylene Blue Removal in Synthetic Wastewater

Numfon Eaktasang, Yanasinee Suma

Article Info

Article History

Received:
April 10, 2022

Accepted:
November 11, 2022

Keywords :

Activated carbon, Bio-waste, Methylene blue, Water hyacinth

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.7311806

Abstract

The aim of this research was to investigate the efficiency of methylene blue removal in synthetic wastewater using adsorption processes of activated carbon prepared from water hyacinth. The water hyacinth was selected as a bio-waste material to prepare adsorbent by carbonization method at the optimum temperature of 350 °C. The results found optimal conditions of the adsorption performance of water hyacinth activated carbon (WHAC) at the initial pH of 5.0, initial concentration of methylene blue of 80 mg/L, contact time of 30 min and adsorbent dosage of 100 mg at 250°C. The methylene blue adsorption experiment was fitted with Langmuir isotherm model ($R^2 = 0.9489$) with a maximum adsorption capacity of 18.4162 mg/g. These findings proposed that WHAC is an alternative adsorbent for dyes removal from wastewater.

Introduction

Wastewater discharge from textile industries without proper treatment can cause of water pollution (i.e. toxicological and aesthetic) and harm to aquatic life (Hamad and Idrus, 2022). Various types of dyes and chemicals are used in the textile manufacturing process. Dyes are substances obtained from natural and non-natural or synthetic sources. Natural dyes have a narrow range of colors, low fastness to fabrics, and fade on washing whereas synthetic dyes provide a wide color range (Mekuria et al., 2022). Therefore, the synthetic dyes were preferred for used in textile products. Dyes found in effluent had an impact on water quality, such as reducing light transmission into aquatic systems, and their appearance color may be unsuitable for human consumption (Shakoor and Nasar, 2016). The removal process of dyes from wastewater was required. The various treatment methods were employed to remove dyes in wastewater, such as adsorption, coagulation-flocculation, and ion exchange (Asgher and Bhatti, 2012; Quansah et al., 2020). Adsorption methods are widely used for dyes treatment in terms of cost-effectiveness and recyclability (Siddiqui et al., 2019; Fito et al., 2020). Especially, carbon nanotubes, biochar, graphite carbon, activated carbon, modified activated carbon, and porous carbon, in particular, were used as adsorbents for dye removal. The adsorbent was composed primarily of agro-waste (83%), with coal and wood accounting for 9% and 2%, respectively (Hamad and Idrus, 2022). Although, the commercial activated carbon was attractive for adsorbents, it was also expensive and required investment for preparation and recycling (Ali et al., 2022). A previous study reported that the agricultural waste materials being prepared for activated carbon include rice husk, peanut hull, palm shell, coconut shell, tropical wood, corncob, saw dust, and pistachio shells (De Luna et al., 2013). Therefore, the development of bio-material for adsorbent is still an attractive choice for dyes removal.

Water hyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes*) is an aquatic plant which causes of water pollution during blooming season, such as clogging waterways, reducing light transmission, blocking the air-water interface and reducing oxygen levels in the water. Water hyacinth (WH) rapidly grows in water that enriches the nutrients, and the mats of WH can expand by double from their original size in 6-18 days. The river and channel where received water discharge from household areas. It was abundant in nitrogen and phosphorus as the nutrient source of WH. Generally, the WH was controlled by collecting from water and dumping it on the land area. In addition, WH can be used as the raw material for making WH baskets and compost. To solve the problem of WH and increase the value of WH bio-waste, the adsorbent material made from WH was interesting due to its low cost and environmental friendliness.

Therefore, the aim of this study was to prepare activated carbon from WH by the carbonization process. The carbonized temperature was varied at 250-550 °C. The structure and performance of water hyacinth activated carbon (WHAC) were analyzed by Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FESEM). The surface area of WHAC was measured by Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method (Ali et al., 2022). The adsorption capacity of

WHAC was investigated by varying the pH, dye concentrations, contact time and adsorbent dosage. The representative dye solution was methylene blue (Mekuria et al., 2022) due to a typical cationic dye that is usually used for dyeing cotton, wool, and silk (Liu et al., 2021). The adsorption efficiency was measured by the methylene blue concentration using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer. In addition, the adsorption isotherm was studied.

Materials and Methods

Chemical Preparation

All chemicals were purchased at analytical grade. Methylene blue (MB) was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. The stock solution of MB was prepared (1,000 mg/L) by dissolving 1 g of MB in deionized water (Ali et al., 2022). The different concentrations of MB were prepared by diluting the stock solution. The pH of solution was adjusted using 0.1 M HCl and 0.1 M NaOH solution. All solutions were prepared in deionized water.

Water Hyacinth Plant

The raw WH was collected from the Chao Phraya river, Sam Khok, Pathumthai province. The collected WH was thoroughly washed with water to remove other contaminants. The stem of WH was collected and cut into small pieces of 2 cm., and dried by sunlight for 3 days, then continuously dried in a hot air oven at 60°C for 3 days to remove the moisture content (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Preparation of raw water hyacinth

Preparation of Water Hyacinth Activated Carbon

The preparation of activated carbon, the dried WH was put in ceramic crucible and carbonized at different temperatures (250-550 °C) for 1 hour, and allowed to cool down at room temperature in a desiccator. WHAC was grinded and sieved to obtain a homogenous with a particle size of 1-2 mm. (Figure 2). The adsorption capacity of WHAC was measured by the Iodine number method (ASTM D4607-14, 2021).

Figure 2. Preparation of water hyacinth activated carbon

Instrumental Analysis

The WHAC morphology was analyzed using a field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM) (JEOL, JSM 7800F, Japan). The surface area of WHAC was characterized by Brunauer-Emmet-Teller (BET) method (Micromeritics, TriStar II 3020, USA). The MB concentration was measured by a UV-VIS spectrophotometer (Shimadzu-2450, Japan) with a wavelength at 665 nm. (Liu et al., 2021).

Adsorption Experiments

Effect of pH

The effect of pH was varied at 3, 5, 7, and 9 with fixed conditions of 100 mL of MB solution (10 mg/L) and 50 mg of WHAC. Then, the solutions were allowed to shake for 1 hour at 80 rpm. at 25 °C. After shaking, all the solution was filtered through filter paper (Whatman). The filtrate solutions were analyzed by a UV-VIS spectrophotometer.

Effect of Initial MB Concentration

The initial concentration of MB was varied at 20, 40, 60, and 80 mg/L with volume of 100 mL, 50 mg of WHAC and optimum pH that obtained from pH effect experiment. Then, the solutions were allowed to shake for 1 hour at 80 rpm. at 25 °C. After shaking, all the solution was filtered through filter paper (Whatman). The filtrate solutions were analyzed by a UV-VIS spectrophotometer.

Effect of Contact Time

The contact time was varied at 5, 15, 30, 45, 60, and 90 min with volume of 100 mL, 50 mg of WHAC and optimum pH and initial concentration of MB that obtained from pH and initial concentration effect experiments. Then, the solutions were allowed to shake for 1 hour at 80 rpm. at 25 °C. After shaking, all the solution was filtered through filter paper (Whatman). The filtrate solutions were analyzed by a UV-VIS spectrophotometer.

Effect of Adsorbent Dosage

The amount of adsorbent (WHAC) was varied at 10, 30, 50, 100, 300, and 500 mg with 100 mL of solution and optimum pH, initial concentration of MB and contact time that were obtained from pH, initial concentration, and contact time experiments. Then, the solutions were allowed to shake for 1 hour at 80 rpm. at 25 °C. After shaking, all the solution was filtered through filter paper (Whatman). The filtrate solutions were analyzed by a UV-VIS spectrophotometer.

The MB removal efficiency (%) and the MB adsorption capacity (mg/g) were evaluated using Equation 1 and 2, respectively (Mekuria et al., 2022).

$$\text{Removal efficiency (\%)} = \left(\frac{C_0 - C_e}{C_0} \right) \times 100 \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

$$\text{Adsorption capacity (mg/g)} = \left(\frac{C_0 - C_e}{m} \right) \times V \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

Where C_0 and C_e are the initial and equilibrium concentrations of MB solution (mg/L), respectively, m is the mass (g) of the adsorbent, and V is the volume of solution (L).

Adsorption Isotherms

The adsorption isotherm was analyzed by the Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms. The Langmuir isotherm is applicable when monolayer adsorption occurs on the material surface with a small number of identical sites. This model concludes a uniform and equally disseminated adsorption on the surface and no transmigration on the flat surface. The dimension separation factor (R_L) can be applied to express the basic characteristics of Langmuir. The Freundlich isotherm assumes a heterogeneous surface with non-uniform heat of bio-sorption transmission through the surface suggestion multilayer bio-sorption (Farghali et al., 2020). Table 1 shows the isotherm equations.

Table 1. Equations and parameters of isotherm models

Model	Linear Equation
Langmuir	$\frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{1}{q_m K_L} + \frac{C_e}{q_m}$
	$R_L = \frac{1}{1 + K_L C_0}$
Freundlich	$\log q_e = \log K_F + \frac{1}{n} \log C_e$

Where q_m is the maximum adsorption capacity, C_e is equilibrium concentration, q_e is equilibrium adsorption capacity, K_L is the Langmuir constant, K_F and n are Freundlich constants. C_0 is the highest concentration of MB (mg/L) and R_L is the value that determines the kind of isotherm. It will be linear when $R_L = 1$, irreversible when $R_L = 0$, unfavorable if R_L is higher than 1, or favorable if it is higher than 0 and less than 1 (Ali et al., 2022).

Results and Discussion

Characterization of WHAC

Effect of Carbonization Temperature

The WHAC was prepared at different carbonization temperatures (250-550 °C) as shown in Figure 3. The carbonization at 350 °C was homogeneous color and morphology when compared to other temperatures. The results of adsorption capacity of WHAC by Iodine number measurement was supported the optimum temperature at 350 °C. The Iodine number of 1,489.5, 1,335.2 and 1,258.9 mg/g was carbonized temperature at 350 °C, 400 °C and 300 °C, respectively. The lowest of Iodine number was obtained at a carbonized temperature of 250 °C. The carbonized temperature of WHAC in this study was similarly to previous research as it prepared the porous carbons from garlic peel (Huang et al., 2020). Otherwise, the optimum temperature to prepare activated carbon in this study was lower when compared to previous studies (Liu et al., 2021; Ali et al., 2022). The optimum temperature of adsorbent was based on the original structure and characteristics.

Figure 3. Preparation of WHAC at carbonization temperatures of 250-550 °C.

Morphology Analysis

The physical morphology of WHAC was analyzed by using FESEM as presented in Figure 4. The WHAC obtained from varied temperatures of activated carbon preparation was significant changed in the morphology structure. The carbonization temperatures at 250 °C and 300 °C were sheet morphology and non-uniform in structure. The tubes morphology and uniform porous were found at 350 °C and 400 °C, but the porous of WHAC obtained at 400 °C was larger than 350 °C. Furthermore, the carbonized temperature of over 400 °C had a non-uniform of morphology and porous structure. The volatile organic compounds evaporated as the temperature rose, and the material was transformed into carbon. Whereas, the temperature continuously increased, the morphology was damaged, as similar to the previous report (Elkady et al., 2015).

Surface Analysis

The Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method was used to examine the surface area of WHAC. The BET method was employs the adsorption-desorption isotherms of nitrogen for investing surface area. The result of surface

area was presented in Table 2. It was observed that the surface area was increased as the temperature increased. The highest surface area was $5.7013 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ at $350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and followed by $5.1454 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ at $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Whereas, the lowest surface area was $1.9695 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ at $550 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ which was a high carbonized temperature, resulting in non-structural of WHAC and expansion of the porous. The BET result was contributed to FESEM analysis for WHAC, which prepared the optimum carbonized temperature at $350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Table 2. Surface area analysis by BET method of WHAC at carbonization temperatures of 250-550 $^\circ\text{C}$.

Surface Area (m^2/g)	Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)						
	250	300	350	400	450	500	550
Single point surface area at p/p^0	3.8002	4.1263	5.3136	5.0307	4.1646	2.7173	1.7153
BET surface area	3.9171	4.5403	5.7013	5.1454	4.4259	3.0542	1.9695
Langmuir surface area	7.1038	8.9607	10.6862	9.1385	8.6412	6.5317	4.3848
Micropore area	3.1941	3.0940	3.9791	4.1509	3.2528	2.4364	1.5856
External surface area	3.9098	5.8667	6.7071	4.9876	5.3885	4.0953	2.7992

Figure 4. FESEM images of WHAC at carbonization temperatures of 250-550 $^\circ\text{C}$.

The characteristics analysis of activated carbon prepared from WH by varying the carbonized temperature during 250-550 $^\circ\text{C}$ was found the optimum temperature at $350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Therefore, the WHAC obtained at $350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was used in the adsorption capacity of the MB experiment.

MB Removal Efficiency on WHAC

The influences of the parameters on adsorption efficiency, including pH, MB concentration, contact time and adsorbent dosage were examined.

Effect of pH

The pH effect on MB adsorption using WHAC was examined in the pH range of 3-9 at 25⁰C as shown in Figure 5. The MB removal efficiency increased as the pH was changed from 3 to 5, then decreased at pH 7 to 9. The pH 5 was at its maximum removal efficiency (90.2%). The pH of the solution was affected by charges on the adsorbent surface as well as the ionization degree of various contaminants. The increase in the adsorbent negative surface charge, the cationic dye like MB adsorption is usually supposed to rise with the increase in pH (Ali et al., 2022). Therefore, the pH of the MB solution (pH = 5) was considered as the optimum pH for further experiments.

Figure 5. pH effect on removal efficiency of MB on WHAC at 25⁰C.

Effect of Initial MB Concentration

The MB initial concentration of 20, 40, 60, and 80 mg/L was examined at pH 5, which was obtained from a prior experiment of pH effect. As a result, the removal efficiency was increased with the concentration of adsorbate increasing, which was similar to the previous report (Mekuria et al., 2022). The removal efficiency ranged from 85.6 to 95.2%, from 20 mg/L to 80 mg/L. The relationship between adsorbates and adsorbents improved since the initial dye concentration increased, which could be assumed that a higher concentration can effectively increase the elimination of MB adsorption process (Ali et al., 2022). Hence, the initial concentration of MB (80 mg/L) was considered as the optimum concentration for further experiments.

Figure 6. The effect of initial dye concentration on MB removal efficiency on WHAC at 25⁰C.

Effect of Contact Time

The contact time of 5, 15, 30, 45, 60, and 90 min was examined at pH 5 and MB initial concentration of 80 mg/L. As a result, the removal efficiency was increased during the initial experiment from 5 to 30 min, then gradually declined and became to stable (Figure 7). This result shows that the equilibrium adsorption was obtained in 30 min on WHAC. However, increasing the contact time had no influence on the MB adsorption. This finding was different from previous studies that found the equilibrium of 60 min (Ali et al., 2022), 45 min (Barka et al., 2011), and 20 min (Mekuria et al., 2022) for MB adsorption. The rapid initial adsorption was the most binding sites on WHAC was available, which resulted in the quick binding of adsorbate molecules. As the binding site is occupied, the adsorption rate becomes accordingly slow because of the competition to occupy the available sites by MB (Cheruiyot et al., 2019). Therefore, the contact time of 30 min was considered as an optimum time for further experiments.

Figure 7. The effect of contact time on the removal efficiency of MB on WHAC at 25 °C.

Effect of Adsorbent Dosage

The amount of adsorbent (WHAC) of 10, 30, 50, 100, 300, 500 mg was observed at pH 5, MB initial concentration of 80 mg/L and contact time of 30 min. The result was found to be that the removal efficiency was increased in dosages of 10-100 mg and that there was gradual decrease by increasing the adsorbent dosage. The increase of adsorbent is similar to increasing binding sites for adsorbate. Otherwise, the occupied site was limited by MB molecules. Therefore, the rising binding site has not influenced MB removal. This finding was supported by the adsorbent dosage effect of the previous study (Ali et al., 2022).

Figure 8. The effect of adsorbent dosage on removal efficiency of MB on WHAC at 25 °C.

Adsorption Isotherm

The adsorption isotherms study was used to calculate the adsorption model of Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms. The results of Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms are demonstrated in Figure 9 and 10, respectively. Figure 9 indicates that the applicability of the Langmuir isotherm model with a correlation coefficient (R^2) of 0.9489 for MB on WHAC. Based on the Langmuir equation, the q_m for MB on WHAC was 18.4162 mg/g. The value of K_L obtained from the plot was 0.2244 L/mg for WHAC. The model applicability indicates that the adsorbate monolayer adsorption on the outer surface of the adsorbent is a significant factor. The value of R_L was found to be of in the range of 0.0528-0.1822 for MB adsorption on WHAC. According to the data plot followed by the Freundlich adsorption isotherm (Figure 10), an R^2 of 0.84409 was shown. The value of the intercept K_F obtained from the plot was 0.3109. The slope value ($1/n$) derived from the plot was 4.4016. The value of K_F shows the adsorption capacity, and $1/n$ determines the adsorption intensity. These findings indicated that the adsorbent had several different types of adsorption sites (Ali et al., 2022). As a result, it could be proved that the Langmuir isotherm model was more favorable as compared to the Freundlich isotherm model.

Figure 9. Langmuir adsorption isotherm of MB on WHAC at 25 °C.

Figure 10. Freundlich adsorption isotherm of MB on WHAC at 25 °C.

Table 3. Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms analysis parameter.

Model	Parameter	R^2
Langmuir isotherm	q_m (mg/g)	18.4162
	K_L (L/mg)	0.2244
	R_L	0.0528-0.1822
Freundlich isotherm	K_F (mg/g)(L/mg) ^{1/n}	0.3109
	1/n	4.4016

The effectiveness of WHAC adsorbents was compared to bio-based activated carbon (Table 4). In this study, the q_{max} of WHAC of MB was comparable to previous studies and also lower than some studies. The maximum adsorption capacity prepared from bio-materials for MB was varied in different conditions, e.g. pH value, temperature, and dose.

Table 4. Adsorption capacity of activated carbon for MB adsorption.

Adsorbent (Activated carbon)	Maximum adsorption capacity, q_{max} (mg/g)	References
Wheat shell	16.6	Bulut and Aydin, 2006
Neem leaf powder	8.8	Mohammed et al., 2014
Corn cob	165.0	Reddy et al., 2016
Coconut leaves	250.0	Jawad et al., 2017
Rice husk	21.9	Phihusut and Chantharat, 2017
Cotton pulp	461.8	Liu et al., 2021
Sisal hemp pulp	490.9	Liu et al., 2021
<i>Datura metels</i> seeds	154.5	Ali et al., 2022
<i>Hordeum vulgare</i> bran	63.2	Mekuria et al., 2022
<i>Ensete ventricosum</i> midrib leaf	35.5	Mekuria et al., 2022
Water hyacinth	18.42	This study

Conclusion

This study, bio-waste derived adsorbent was WH for removal MB in synthetic wastewater. WHAC was prepared at carbonized temperature range of 250-550^oC. Then the prepared WHAC was used for removal of MB by varying the different parameters that included pH, initial concentration of MB, contact time and adsorbent dosage. The carbonized temperature at 350 ^oC was found in the maximum adsorption capacity and surface area. The optimum conditions of MB adsorption were pH 5, initial concentration of 80 mg/L, contact time of 30 min, and an adsorbent dosage of 100 mg. An adsorption isotherm was fitted to the Langmuir isotherm as compared to the Freundlich isotherm. In conclusion, these findings demonstrated that activated carbon prepared from WH is a promising alternative for the removal of MB, which is a cationic dye from wastewater.

Acknowledgements

This study was funded by the Faculty of Public Health, Thammasat University.

References

- ASTM D4607-14. Standard Test Method for Determination of Iodine Number of Activated Carbon. 2021.
- Ali, J., Bakhsh, E.M., Hussain, N., Bilal, M., Akhtar, K., Fagieh, T. M., Danish, E.Y., Asiri, A.M. & Su, X. (2022). A new bioresource for synthesis of activated carbon and its potential use for removal of methylene blue and eriochrome black T from aqueous solutions. *Industrial Crops & Products*, 179(2022), 114676, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2022.114676>
- Asgher, M. & Bhatti, H.N. (2012). Evaluation of thermodynamics and effect of chemical treatments on sorption potential of *Citrus* waste biomass for removal of anionic dyes from aqueous solutions. *Ecological Engineering*, 38(1), 79-85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2011.10.004>
- Barka, N., Abdennouri, M. & Makhfouk, M.EL. (2011). Removal of methylene blue and eriochrome black T from aqueous solutions by biosorption on *Scolymus hispanicus* L.: Kinetics, equilibrium and thermodynamics. *Journal of the Taiwan Institute of Chemical Engineers*. 42(2), 320-326. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtice.2010.07.004>
- Bulut, Y. & Aydin, H. (2006). A kinetics and thermodynamics study of methylene blue adsorption on wheat shells. *Desalination*. 194(1-3), 259-267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2005.10.032>
- Cheruiyot, G.K., Wanyonyi, W.C., Kiplimo, J. & Maina, E.N. (2019). Adsorption of toxic crystal violet dye using coffee husks: Equilibrium, kinetics and thermodynamics study. *Scientific African*. 5, e00116, 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2019.e00116>
- De Luna, M.D., Flores, E.D., Genuino, D.A.D., Futralan, C.M. & Wan, M.W. (2013). Adsorption of Eriochrome Black T (EBT) dye using activated carbon prepared from waste rice hulls-Optimization, isotherm and kinetic studies. *Journal of Taiwan Institute of Chemical Engineers*. 44(4), 646-653. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtice.2013.01.010>
- Elkady, M.F., Hussein, M.H. & Atiaa, H.M. (2015). Preparation of nano-activated carbon from carbon based material for copper decontamination from wastewater. *American Journal of Applied Chemistry*. 3(3-1), 31-37. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ajac.s.2015030301.15>
- Farghali, R.A., Sobhi, M., Gaber, S.E., Ibrahim, H. & Elshehy, E.A. (2020). Adsorption of organochlorine pesticides on modified porous Al₃₀/bentonite: Kinetic and thermodynamic studies. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*. 13(8), 6730-6740. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arabjc.2020.06.027>
- Fito, J., Abrham, S. & Angassa, K. (2020). Adsorption of methylene blue from textile industrial wastewater onto activated carbon of *Parthenium hysterophorus*. *International Journal of Environmental Research*. 14, 501-511. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41742-020-00273-2>
- Hamad, H.N. & Idrus, S. (2022). Recent developments in the application of bio-waste-derived adsorbents for the removal of methylene blue from wastewater: A review. *Polymer*. 14(4), 783, 1-39. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14040783>
- Huang, G., Wu, X., Hou, Y. & Cai, J. (2020). Sustainable porous carbons from garlic peel biowaste and KOH activation with an excellent CO₂ adsorption performance. *Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery*. 10, 267-276. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13399-019-00412-6>
- Jawad, A.H., Sabar, S., Ishak, M.A.M, Wilson, L.D. & Norrahma, S.S.A. (2017). Microwave-assisted preparation of mesoporous-activated carbon from coconut (*Cocos nucifera*) leaf by H₃PO₄ activation for methylene blue adsorption. *Chemical Engineering Communications*. 204(10), 1143-1156. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00986445.2017.1347565>
- Liu, B., Du, C., Chen, J.J., Zhai, J.Y., Wang, Y. & Li, H.L. (2021). Preparation of well-developed mesoporous activated carbon fibers from plant pulp fibers and its adsorption of methylene blue from solution. *Chemical Physics Letters*. 771, 138535, 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cplett.2021.138535>

- Mekuria, D., Diro, A., Melak, F. & Asere, T.G. (2022). Adsorption removal of methylene blue dye using biowaste materials: barley bran and enset midrib leaf. *Journal of Chemistry*. 2022, 4849758, 1-13 <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/4849758>
- Mohammed, M.A., Shitu, S. & Ibrahim, A. (2014). Removal of methylene blue using low cost adsorbent: A review. *Research Journal of Chemical Sciences*. 4(1), 91-102. www.isca.me
- Pihusut, D. & Chantharat, M. (2017). Removal of methylene blue using agricultural waste: A case study of rice husk and rice husk ash from Chaipattana Rice Mill Demonstration Center. *Environment and Natural Resources Journal*. 15(2), 30-38. <https://ph02.tci-thaijo.org/index.php/ennrj/article/view/89349>
- Quansah, J.O., Hlaing, T., Lyonga, F.N., Kyi, P.P., Hong, S.H., Lee, C.G. & Park, S.J. (2020). Nascent rice husk as an adsorbent for removing cationic dyes from textile wastewater. *Applied Sciences*. 10(10), 3437. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10103437>
- Reddy, P.M.K., Verma, P. & Subrahmanyam, C. (2016). Bio-waste derived adsorbent material for methylene blue adsorption. *Journal of the Taiwan Institute of Chemical Engineers*. 58, 500-508. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtice.2015.07.006>
- Shahoor, S. & Nasar, A. (2016). Removal of methylene blue dye from artificially contaminated water using citrus limetta peel waste as a very low cost adsorbent. *Journal of the Taiwan Institute of Chemical Engineers*. 66, 154-163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtice.2016.06.009>
- Siddiqui, S.I., Fatima, B., Tara, N., Rathi, G. & Chaudhry, S.A. (2019). 15-Recent advances in remediation of synthetic dyes from wastewaters using sustainable and low-cost adsorbents. *The Impact and Prospects of Green Chemistry for Textile Technology*. Woodhead Publishing, 471-507. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-102491-1.00015-0>

Author Information

Numfon Eaktasang*

Faculty of Public Health, Thammasat University
99, M.18, Paholyothin Road, Piyachart Building,
Khlung 1, Khlung Luang, Pathumthani, 12121,
Thailand

Yanasinee Suma

Faculty of Public Health, Thammasat University
(Lampang Campus)
248, M2, Lampang-Chiang Mai Road,
Pongyangkhok,
Hangchat, Lampang, 52190, Thailand
